

reactions to BI followed an almost normal distribution; in reactions to BB, susceptible types MS, S, and HS prevailed. BI-resistant types MR and R (76.31%) dominated in 1988 because almost half the resistant combinations were derived from Minghui 63, a

resistant R-line.

Most of the 20 hybrids tested both years were resistant to BI. All combinations from A-lines and all R-lines except Xiuhui 2, Ce 49, and Pinghui 3 were susceptible to BB. Disease severity by inoculation was

consistent with that in the plots. Most hybrids were susceptible to FS in at least 1 yr and in a plot.

Disease resistance in hybrid rice is determined by the parents. A-lines currently available are not resistant. □

Changes in total phenols in rice varieties inoculated with *Rhizoctonia solani* and treated with carbendazim

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We inoculated rice varieties ADT31, CR1009, AU42/1, IR20, and White Ponni with *R. solani* at maximum tillering (80 d old) by single sclerotium method in an experiment during 1985 samba season (Aug-Jan). Fungicide (0.1 % carbendazim) was sprayed 3 d after inoculation (DAI). Portions of the plant sheath were sampled 3, 5, and 7 DAI and 3, 5, and 7 d after fungicide application and analyzed for changes in total phenolic content.

Changes in total phenolics after *R. solani* inoculation and carbendazim application. Annamalai University, India, 1985.

Days after inoculation and fungicide application	Treatment	Total phenolic content ^a					
		ADT31	CR1009	AU42/1	IR20	White ponni	Mean
3	Healthy	2.89	3.07	3.02	3.10	3.04	3.02
	Inoculated	3.17	3.26	3.19	3.25	3.18	3.21
	Fungicide treated	3.68	3.88	3.85	3.92	3.76	3.82
5	Healthy	2.78	2.95	2.87	2.94	2.88	2.88
	Inoculated	3.01	3.13	3.08	3.16	3.05	3.09
	Fungicide treated	3.48	3.68	3.56	3.71	3.59	3.60
7	Healthy	2.68	2.78	2.78	2.87	2.74	2.79
	Inoculated	2.84	3.04	2.92	3.02	2.85	2.93
	Fungicide treated	3.23	3.37	3.18	3.30	3.12	3.24

^a In mg/g of tissue on dry weight basis in catechol equivalent.

Highly susceptible ADT31 contained less total phenols than susceptible CR1009, AU42/1, IR20, and White Ponni (see table). Total

phenolic content in all varieties increased with *R. solani* inoculation and with fungicide application, but decreased with plant age. □

Conditions for sporulation of rice blast (BI) fungus

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We studied the effects of 17 media and 3 irradiation levels on sporulation of 41 isolates of rice BI fungus (*Pyricularia oryzae*) during 1986-87. All isolates were grown on yeast starch agar and kept in an incubator at 28 °C.

Cultures were irradiated continuously at a distance of 30 cm from the lamp.

Test tubes containing 5 ml each of different media were inoculated by putting a 3 mm² piece of mycelial agar

Table 1. Effect of growth medium on sporulation of rice BI fungus. Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Medium	Mean sporulation ^a (10 ⁴ conidia/ml)
Cornmeal rice straw agar	(40, 50, 20) ^b 27.89 a
Rice leaf potato agar	(100, 200, 20) ^c 11.93 b
Rice straw agar	(100, 20) ^c 11.91 b
Oatmeal agar	(40, 20) 10.68 c
Cornmeal agar	(50, 20) 9.46 d
Corn leaf potato agar	(100, 200, 20) ^c 9.23 d
Rice bran rice leaf agar	(20, 50, 20) 8.85 d
Rice leaf agar	(100, 20) ^d 7.83 e
Rice bran agar	(20, 20) 5.94 f
Rice polish agar	(20, 20) 5.61 fg
Cornmeal beef extract agar	(40, 40, 20) ^d 5.13 gh
Prune agar	(1, 20) ^e 4.48 hi
Yeast starch agar	(2, 10, 20) 4.26 i
Barley agar	(50, 20) ^c 3.51 j
Potato agar	(200, 20) 3.13 j
V-8 juice rice straw agar	(250, 50, 20) ^f 2.89 j
Protein peptone yeast agar	(10, 5, 20) 1.45 k

^a Av of 2 replications of 41 isolates. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^b Contains 40 g cornmeal, 50 g rice straw, 20 g agar, 1000 ml distilled water. ^c Plus 20 g sucrose. ^d Plus 10 g glucose. ^e 1 g lactose, 1 g yeast extract. ^f Plus 3 g CaCO₃.